

NERO

POST WEBINAR REPORT

NERO Marketplace Demonstration Webinar Cybersecurity Solutions & Training for SMEs

WEBINAR

29 October 2025

15:00 – 16:00 CET

NERO
Marketplace

NERO
Training

Funded by
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ECCC
EUROPEAN CYBERSECURITY
COMPETENCE CENTRE

Webinar Overview

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) face distinct cybersecurity challenges driven by limited financial and human resources. With tight budgets, many cannot afford advanced security infrastructure or dedicated IT staff, often relying on basic or consumer-grade solutions that leave them exposed to sophisticated threats. Low cybersecurity awareness among employees further increases vulnerability to phishing and social engineering attacks.

The rise of automated, AI-driven, and malware-as-a-service attacks has intensified these risks, while compliance with evolving data protection regulations adds another layer of difficulty. Many SMEs struggle to understand and implement the required measures, leading to potential fines or reputational damage.

The NERO project aims to address these challenges by offering a marketplace for cybersecurity tools and training programmes. Through the NERO marketplace, SMEs can find exactly the tools they need from a varied collection of open-source cybersecurity tools and low-cost tools from EU vendors. Next to the cybersecurity tools, SMEs can find tailored training courses on various cybersecurity topics as well as on the tools themselves.

In October 2025, the NERO Cybersecurity team hosted the [“NERO Marketplace Demonstration Webinar”](#) – a combined training and demonstration session designed to help SMEs navigate the NERO Marketplace, explore cybersecurity tools and programs, and identify practical solutions to strengthen their digital defences.

During the webinar, the marketplace and its functionalities were introduced. Moreover, two tools from the NERO marketplace were presented: Snyk and Deep Guardian. The session was then rounded off by showcasing how the two tools can be chained together in a real-life scenario.

This webinar highlighted insights and cybersecurity tools from our speakers:

Wissam Mallouli is a Senior Researcher, Project Manager, and CTO at **Montimage (France)**, specialising in cybersecurity, AI-driven monitoring, and resilience in complex systems. He has coordinated and contributed to numerous European research projects in the areas of network security, trust management, and smart systems. Within **NERO**, he serves as **WP3 Leader**, coordinating the development of the NERO Marketplace.

Eleni Seralidou is a Project Manager at **Trustilio B.V.**, specialising in cybersecurity, secure software development, code auditing, and vulnerability assessment. She is a certified **ISO 27001:2022 ISMS Lead Auditor** and has authored multiple scientific publications in conferences and journals since 2010. Within **NERO**, she serves as the **Project Co-Coordinator**.

Pedro Tomás is a Project Manager at **OneSource** and is currently pursuing a **PhD at the University of Coimbra**, focusing on the detection of anomalies in cloud-native environments. His research interests include Federated Learning, Root Cause Analysis, Adversarial Machine Learning, and Explainable AI. Within **NERO**, OneSource leads the **Exploitation activities** and provides **DeepGuardian**, a Network Intrusion Detection and Prevention System (NIDPS).

Ole Höfener holds a **Master of Science in Information Security** from **Stockholm University**. Within **NERO**, he leads the project's **training activities**. In addition, Ole is involved in product management for **MDS's learning platform KIOKU**.

NERO Audience and Participation

The webinar was free to attend and attracted a diverse audience from various disciplines, including representatives from SMEs, academia, researchers, national authorities, EU institutions, industry professionals and organisations from across Europe. Below, you'll discover a detailed breakdown of registrants and attendees categorised by stakeholder type.

 Registrants: 47

 Attendees: 33

 Duration: 60 mins

Registrants by stakeholder

Country Representation

The NERO Marketplace and Training

The [NERO Marketplace](#) offers a curated range of innovative cybersecurity tools and software designed to help organisations protect, monitor, and strengthen their digital infrastructure. From advanced threat detection and response solutions to compliance management tools, the platform connects SMEs with trusted technologies that enhance resilience against evolving cyber threats. Users can explore, compare, and identify the most suitable solutions to safeguard their business and build a stronger cybersecurity posture.

Besides cybersecurity tools, the **NERO Marketplace** also offers a wide range of training courses. Some focus on various topics within the cybersecurity domain, while others are specific to the tools available on the marketplace. Through this, the NERO Marketplace provides SMEs with a curated and affordable way to strengthen their cybersecurity capacity and become familiar with the available tools.

Training & Live Demonstration Highlights

The NERO Marketplace Demonstration Webinar showcased the platform's key features and functionalities, offering participants a guided tour of how to discover, compare, and adopt trusted cybersecurity tools and training courses. The session provided SMEs with practical insights into how the NERO Marketplace can support their efforts to strengthen cybersecurity capacity and become familiar with available solutions.

Here are the highlights from the speakers' presentations.

Wissam Mallouli, Montimage

Wissam highlighted that the NERO Marketplace targets the 98% of European companies that are SMEs, which often lack affordable and easy-to-use cybersecurity solutions. It provides tailored cybersecurity tools and training, integrates with Moodle for quick access to learning content, and features an open, modular architecture that supports new tool onboarding and EU marketplace connections. Emphasising European data sovereignty, it offers sector-specific solutions for healthcare, finance, and transport. Future goals include expanding the tool catalogue, involving external contributors, and ensuring long-term sustainability. For example, a healthcare SME can use Snyk for secure software development and DeepGuardian to monitor network traffic and detect intrusions.

Eleni Seralidou, TRUSTILIO B.V.

Eleni presented a demonstration of **Snyk**, a developer-first security platform that integrates seamlessly into DevSecOps workflows. Snyk scans for vulnerabilities across source code, open-source dependencies, containers, and infrastructure-as-code (IaC).

It embeds security directly into development pipelines such as GitHub, GitLab, and CI/CD systems, automates vulnerability detection, and can block insecure builds. The platform uses a priority scoring system based on CVSS combined with proprietary algorithms that consider factors like exploit maturity and fixability. By promoting a “shift-left” approach, Snyk enables developers to address vulnerabilities early in the development process rather than after deployment.

The key benefits include faster time to market, continuous security monitoring, empowered developers with less reliance on dedicated security teams, and significant cost savings through early issue detection.

Pedro Tomás, ONESOURCE

Pedro presented a demonstration of **DeepGuardian**, a cloud-native intrusion detection and prevention system (IDPS) designed for distributed, Kubernetes-based environments. DeepGuardian leverages AI and federated learning to perform real-time anomaly detection without sharing sensitive data, addressing the limitations of traditional rule-based systems that struggle with modern, dynamic cloud setups.

Its architecture consists of several key components: the Core (the machine learning engine), Collector and Agent (for data collection and model training), Dashboard (for visual insights), and Policy Enforcer (utilising OPA and Istio). Through federated learning, DeepGuardian preserves data privacy by sharing only model weights rather than raw data, while human-in-the-loop feedback continuously improves model accuracy.

For SMEs, DeepGuardian is particularly valuable because it is scalable, privacy-preserving, affordable, and provides real-time visibility of attacks and network anomalies, all while requiring minimal cybersecurity expertise.

In a typical integration scenario, **Snyk** can be used during development for code auditing, while **DeepGuardian** monitors and protects the network in production. Together, the two tools enable continuous security throughout the CI/CD pipeline.

Panel Session

The audience expressed interest in understanding the practical and strategic aspects of implementing cybersecurity solutions through the NERO Marketplace. Here are some of the interesting questions raised during the event.

Q: How does the DeepGuardian agent monitor an application's network traffic? Does it influence the traffic, e.g., increase latency?

Pedro provided an answer to this question, stating that no, it does not increase latency. Essentially, what we are doing is taking into account the specific characteristics of a cloud-native infrastructure. We capture the network traffic directly from the primary interface of the microservice — specifically, from the primary container — and process it from there.

We use a Python-based script to collect the data, leveraging a known feature vector derived from a predefined dataset. I hope this clarifies your question.

Q: Beyond simply discovering and comparing tools on the NERO Marketplace, how do you envision SMEs effectively measuring and validating the real-world impact (in terms of risk reduction, cost avoidance or process improvement) of adopting those cybersecurity solutions and training programmes offered through the platform?

Eleni said in response to the question. In our marketplace, we offer a wide range of solutions that you are welcome to explore. Anyone interested can visit the marketplace and review the available tools and services.

To measure their impact, users can track key metrics such as incident rates, downtime, or compliance costs before and after adopting the NERO cybersecurity tools available through our marketplace — as well as through our training programs. Additionally, organizations can rely on independent audits or internal reviews to validate improvements in risk reduction and cost efficiency.

The marketplace is open for you to explore and adapt the available solutions to your specific needs. That's my main suggestion.

Perhaps I can add something relevant here — within the NERO project, we are conducting exactly this type of assessment across three sectors: transport, health, and finance. In these sectors, several companies are already using the marketplace to select tools tailored to their specific scenarios. We are currently assessing real KPIs to validate the impact of using the NERO marketplace on these organisations.

The lessons learned from this experience will be shared on our website so that other companies can benefit and follow similar approaches for their own validation and improvement efforts.

 Q: Is there any document, guideline, or standard protocol/architecture to be followed to make our tools available on the marketplace?

Wissam thanked Nicola for the question and said that it was an excellent question. One of our main goals in this project is to expand the marketplace with external tools and training. This process will start in early 2026, and we're now preparing the necessary procedures.

An endorsement team within the NERO consortium is defining the selection criteria and guidelines for submissions. These will soon be published on our website and promoted via social media.

Interested organisations will be able to apply, have their tools or training validated, and then create an account on the marketplace to upload, update, or manage their content.

Key Takeaways

The NERO Marketplace Demonstration Webinar provided participants with valuable insights into how the platform empowers SMEs to strengthen their cybersecurity capacity. The session highlighted the marketplace's key features, diverse resources, and user-friendly design, demonstrating how it streamlines the discovery and adoption of effective cybersecurity solutions.

The NERO Marketplace helps bridge the gap between SMEs' limited cybersecurity capabilities and the growing complexity of modern cyber threats. By offering affordable, easy-to-integrate, and educational tools developed through European collaboration, the platform enables SMEs to adopt practical, trusted solutions. Tools such as Snyk and DeepGuardian exemplify how cybersecurity can serve as an enabler of innovation rather than a barrier to progress.

During the webinar, participants gained a comprehensive understanding of how the NERO Marketplace functions as a one-stop platform where SMEs can explore, compare, and access trusted cybersecurity tools and training courses tailored to their specific needs. The session also emphasised how the platform helps improve SMEs' cybersecurity maturity by providing curated, cost-effective resources that support both skills development and technology adoption. Attendees particularly appreciated the marketplace's intuitive interface and structured categorization, which make it easier to identify relevant tools, assess their applicability, and make informed decisions.

Overall, the demonstration showcased how the NERO Marketplace combines accessibility, education, and practical solutions to help SMEs navigate modern cyber threats, highlighting its potential as a key resource for strengthening cybersecurity across European SMEs.

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Keywords: #Cybersecurity #SMEs #Resilience #Marketplace

SLIDE OF THE PRESENTATIONS AVAILABLE ON ZENODO HERE:

RECORDING OF THE WEBINAR AVAILABLE ON YOUTUBE HERE:

Upcoming Events

The NERO Cybersecurity team is inviting you to join NERO's free, interactive three-part training series designed specifically for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) looking to strengthen their cybersecurity foundations, detect advanced threats, and engage in practical, gamified exercises.

The Hands-On Cybersecurity Training Series for SMEs includes three 90-minute online sessions, each tailored to real-world business needs and designed to help teams build practical, lasting cybersecurity competence.

Session 1: [Building Cybersecurity Awareness and Defence Foundations for SMEs](#) | 26 November 2025

Session 2: [Advanced Threat Detection and Privacy Protection for SMEs](#) | 3 December 2025

Session 3: [Immersive and Gamified Cybersecurity Practices for SMEs](#) | 19 January 2026

Each session offers concise expert presentations, live demonstrations, and engaging discussions that make learning both useful and enjoyable.

Participation is free, but registration is mandatory — and spaces are limited. Don't miss the chance to learn from cybersecurity experts and strengthen your organisation's resilience.

Don't miss out! Learn more and register on the [NERO Cybersecurity website](#).

About NERO Cybersecurity

The NERO consortium is an EC-funded initiative (Grant Agreement No. 101127411) supported by the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC). Its mission is to build stronger, more resilient digital ecosystems across Europe by empowering organisations — especially SMEs — to improve their cybersecurity capabilities.

Bringing together industry specialists, academic researchers, and technology experts, NERO delivers meaningful, hands-on learning experiences that translate complex cybersecurity challenges into actionable strategies. The consortium focuses on sectors such as healthcare, logistics, finance, and digital infrastructure, where awareness and preparedness are key to staying secure.

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